

Supplementary Material

Correspondence

Supplementary Tables

TableS1

TableS2

Homemade Scripts

`sudoParallelGarli.py`

`gapStats.py`

`gapStatsN.py`

`simulateMissingData.py`

Unaligned Datasets in FASTA Format

Multiple Sequence Alignment

Template command line for MSAs

Model Selection

Template command line for model selection in jModelTest2

Phylogenetic Analyses

Template files

Calculation of Match-Split Distances

Template command line for distance calculation in MSdist

Glossary

Supplementary Material

The files mentioned herein are available at zenodo.org, with DOI [10.5281/zenodo.3968770](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3968770). These are supplementary materials of the manuscript “Evidence of Absence Treated as Absence of Evidence: The Effects of Variation in the Number and Distribution of Gaps Treated as Missing Data on the Results of Standard Maximum Likelihood Analysis,” by Denis Jacob Machado, Santiago Castroviejo-Fisher, and Taran Grant.

Contents of README.md (Markdown format) file are also in README.pdf (PDF format).

Correspondence

- Corresponding author: Denis Jacob Machado, Ph.D.
- Email: [dmachado \[at\] uncc \[dot\] edu](mailto:dmachado@uncc.edu) OR [machadodj \[at\] alumni \[dot\] usp \[dot\] br](mailto:machadodj@alumni.usp.br)
- Homepage: <https://about.me/machadodj>

Supplementary Tables

● TableS1

TABLE S1. Analyzed data. Available in `xlsx` and `csv` format.

● TableS2

TABLE S2. Results of the linear model analyses. Available in `xlsx` and `csv` format.

Homemade Scripts

• sudoParallelGarli.py

This script performs sudo-parallelization of Garli. This script was implemented at the ACE computer server (see <https://www.ib.usp.br/grant/anfibios/researchHPC.html>) and leverages on the PBS job scheduler. Read comments on the script for more details.

See <https://gitlab.com/MachadoDJ/sudoparallelgarli> for details.

• gapStats.py

This script will read all FASTA files inside the working directory and print a table containing details statistics into the standard output. The symbol for InDels is “-“. It depends on Biopython.

Execute as follows:

```
1 python gapStats.py
```

• gapStatsN.py

Same as above, except the symbol for indels is “N.”

• simulateMissingData.py

This script adds missing data to an alignment matrix following parameters predefined by the user (replacement probability, percentage of characters to be modified, and percentage of terminals to be modified). It requires an alignment in FASTA format and a cladogram in Newick format. In this script, InDels are represented by “-“ and missing data is represented by “N.” This script depends on Biopython.

Execute as follow:

```
1 python simulateMissingData.py [arguments]
```

The argument `-h` or `--help` gives details on all available arguments:

```
1 usage: simulateMissingData.py [-h] [-v] [-f <FILE_NAME>] [-3 <FILE_NAME>]
2                             [-p <FLOAT>] [-c <FLOAT>] [-t <FLOAT>]
3                             [-r <INTEGER>]
4
5 optional arguments:
6   -h, --help                show this help message and exit
7   -v, --verbose             increase output verbosity
8   -f <FILE_NAME>, --file <FILE_NAME>
9                             input alignment file in FASTA format
10                            (default=alignment.fasta)
11   -3 <FILE_NAME>, --tree <FILE_NAME>
12                            constraints (one dichotomous (sub-)tree in Newick
13                            notation)
14   -p <FLOAT>, --probability <FLOAT>
15                            probability (0 to 1) to replace a nucleotide
16                            (default=0.5)
17   -c <FLOAT>, --characters <FLOAT>
18                            percentage (0 to 1) of characters to be modified
19   -t <FLOAT>, --terminals <FLOAT>
20                            percentage (0 to 1) of terminals to be modified
21   -r <INTEGER>, --replicas <INTEGER>
22                            number of replicas (>=1)
```

Unaligned Datasets in FASTA Format

Dataset #	Reference	Gene	File
1	Wheeler & Hayashi (1998)	18S rDNA	dataset1.fasta
2	Wheeler & Hayashi (1998)	28S rDNA	dataset2.fasta
3	Healy et al. (2009)	18S rDNA	dataset3.fasta
4	Healy et al. (2009)	28S rDNA	dataset4.fasta
5	Wei et al. (2014)	12S rDNA	dataset5.fasta
6	Mauro et al. (2014)	16S rDNA	dataset6.fasta
7	Pozzi et al. (2014)	mtDNA Control Region (CR)	dataset7.fasta
8	Blotto et al. (2013)	CytB	dataset8.fasta

Multiple Sequence Alignment

Multiple-sequence alignments (MSAs) were performed using MAFFT v7.147b.

• Template command line for MSAs

```
1 mafft --nuc --globalpair --maxiterate 1000 --op ${GOC} --ep ${GEC} ${INPUT_FILE} > ${OUTPUT_FILE}
```

Description of variables in the command line above:

- `${GOC}` indicates the gap opening cost (different values, including the default value of 1.53 and the values 0, 0.0956, 0.1913, 0.3825, 0.765, 3.06, 6.12, 12.24, and 24.48)
- `${GEC}` indicates the gap extension cost (this values was always set to 0.123; the default value is zero)
- `${INPUT_FILE}` indicates the input multi-FASTA files
- `${OUTPUT_FILE}` indicates the name of the file that will store the alignment

Model Selection

Selection of the optimal substitution model for each alignment using the corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AICc) was performed in jModelTest v2.1.4.

• Template command line for model selection in jModelTest2

```
1 java -jar jModelTest.jar -d alignment.fasta -g 4 -i -f -AIC -AICc -BIC -DT -a -tr 4 > results.txt
```

Phylogenetic Analyses

Phylogenetic analyses were performed using GARLI v2.01.

• Template files

The following template files were modified for each analysis according to the input files and selected models.

Description	File
Templates for different models for GARLI	garli_model_templates.txt
Template for GARLI's configuration files	garlic_configuration_template.txt

Calculation of Match-Split Distances

Distance calculations were performed using MDdist version 0.5-b158 (see Bogdanowicz & Giaro (2012, <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/5728793/>)). The description of how match split distances are implemented for nonbinary trees is provided in Bogdanowicz & Giaro (2012: 158-159).

• Template command line for distance calculation in MSdist

```
1 java -jar MSdist.jar -m -i cladograms.nwk -o results.txt
```

Glossary

- AICc: Akaike information criterion
- BI: Bayesian inference
- CG: contain gaps
- GCI: gap contiguity index
- GEC: gap extension cost
- GOC: gap opening cost
- ML: maximum likelihood
- MSD: match split distances
- NCI: nucleotide contiguity index
- P: parsimony
- PP: posterior probability
- RF: Robison-Folds (metric)
- SGI: shared gaps index
- TGI: topological gap index
- TIA: trivial identity alignment